

Public transport dashboard using RDF and public APIs

Bachelor Practical Course Data Engineering (INH0021)

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January 20, 2026

Abstract — This project transforms publicly available transport data into a knowledge graph and visualizes it through an interactive application, using RDF. For simplicity, the project focuses on German long-distance trains using both GTFS static data and Deutsche Bahn’s official API. The implementation highlights the potential of semantic technologies for transport information systems, achieving query times under 100ms and processing approximately 30,000 RDF triples across 439 stations.

1 Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
DB	Deutsche Bahn
EC	EuroCity
GTFS	General Transit Feed Specification
IC	InterCity
ICE	InterCity Express
IRI	Internationalized Resource Identifier
ML	Machine Learning
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
UX	User Experience
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XSD	XML Schema Definition
YARRRML	Yet Another RDF Mapping Language

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2 Introduction

The mandatory digitization of public transport in the European Union has led to an increase in the availability of real-time data through public APIs. Transport companies such as Deutsche Bahn and many other public transport operators provide their schedule data free of charge. Using these sources, new and flexible applications can be developed.

2.1 Motivation and Objectives

The project addresses the growing demand for transparent transport information systems. Unlike proprietary solutions, the use of semantic technologies enables data integration from various sources and provides standardized query options via SPARQL. The goal is to implement a complete pipeline that transforms public transport data into a knowledge graph and visualizes it through an interactive application.

2.2 Task Description

The project task is divided into three main components:

(1) **API Analysis** – research and evaluation of public transport APIs regarding their functionality and data quality;

(2) **Knowledge Graph Design** – development of mappings to convert API information into RDF triples;

(3) **Application Development** – implementation of a web application for interaction, visualization, and querying the data via SPARQL and REST.

The implemented system focuses on long-distance trains in Germany and offers real-time departure information, interactive map displays, and mobile applications for iOS and Android, highlighting its adaptability.

3 Theoretical Background

This section introduces the fundamental concepts and technologies for the project: RDF and knowledge graphs, the GTFS data format, YARRRML mappings, and SPARQL query language.

3.1 Semantic Web and RDF

RDF [1] is a W3C standard based on subject-predicate-object triples. Knowledge graphs [12] consist of triples in the form `<subject, predicate, object>`, where subjects and predicates are IRIs, and objects can be IRIs or literals. An ontology [15] defines classes, relationships, and axioms for a domain. This project uses a custom ontology for transport data (Table 1).

Class	Properties / Predicates
TransportStop	hasStopId, hasName, hasLatitude, hasLongitude
TransportDeparture	hasLine, hasDirection, hasPlannedTime, hasPlatform, hasDelay
CachedRoute	hasGeometry, hasCacheKey
TripRoutesCache	hasData

Table 1 Classes and their associated predicates

Example:

```
<stop/631852> a t:TransportStop ;  
  t:hasName "München Hbf" ;  
  t:hasLatitude "48.14" ;  
  t:hasLongitude "11.55" .
```

Design: The ontology prioritizes query efficiency and semantic clarity. The `hasSource` predicate tracks data source (GTFS vs. DB API). XSD datatypes (`xsd:double`, `xsd:dateTime`) ensure type safety and efficient SPARQL filtering.

Benefits: RDF provides flexible schema integration without migrations, standardized SPARQL queries for complex pattern matching, and external linking capabilities. The system processes ~30,000 triples across 439 stations with query times <100ms.

3.2 GTFS and YARRRML

GTFS [3] is an open standard providing information for any method of transport. It contains the following text files: `stops.txt`, `routes.txt`, `trips.txt`, `stop_times.txt`, `calendar.txt`, `shapes.txt`. The platform GTFS.de offered access to the German static transport data for this project. Previous work on Linked GTFS [13] has demonstrated the benefits of representing transit data as linked data.

The project evolved from an initial implementation using Apache Fuseki with manual Java-based mapping to a declarative approach. YARRRML [4] is a YAML-based language for defining RDF mappings declaratively, eliminating the need to write explicit SPARQL INSERT queries or conversion code. Morph-KGC [8], a Python library, executes these mappings and automatically transforms CSV data into RDF triples. Oxigraph [7], a Rust-based SPARQL database, replaced Apache Fuseki due to better performance and a smaller footprint. Listing 1 demonstrates how CSV columns are mapped to typed RDF predicates:

```
1 prefixes:  
2   t: http://transport.example.org/ontology#  
3   xsd: http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#  
4 mappings:  
5   stops:  
6     sources:  
7       - ['data/stops.csv csv']  
8     s: http://transport.example.org/stop/...  
9       $(stop_id)  
10    po:  
11      - [a, t:TransportStop]  
12      - [t:hasStopId, $(stop_id)]  
13      - [t:hasName, $(stop_name)]  
14      - [t:hasLatitude, $(stop_lat)]  
15      - [t:hasLongitude, $(stop_lon)]
```

Listing 1 YARRRML Mapping for Stops

3.3 SPARQL

SPARQL [2] is the standardized query language for RDF data. The project uses SPARQL for querying the database for station, departures, and real-time data. Research on knowledge graphs for public transport [14] has shown the effectiveness of semantic web technologies for this domain.

4 System Architecture

This section describes the system architecture, including the container setup, data flow pipeline, and integration points.

4.1 Overview

The system follows a modern microservice architecture with three Docker containers (Table 2).

Container	Technology	Port
client	React 18 + Vite + nginx	3000
server	FastAPI	8080
oxigraph	Oxigraph RDF Store	3030

Table 2 Docker Container Architecture

4.2 Data Flow Pipeline

The system executes an 8-step pipeline at startup:

Figure 1 Data flow pipeline sequence

5 Data Sources

The system integrates data from two complementary sources: GTFS.de for static schedule information and the Deutsche Bahn API for real-time updates.

5.1 GTFS.de

The dataset is derived from open German transport data sourced from GTFS.de. It originally contains all public transport within the DB network over a 48-hour period, before being filtered to include only long-distance trains.

Unfiltered: 433,000+ stops, 24,000+ routes, 1.5M+ trips.

Filtered: 439 stops, ~150 routes, ~15,000 trips, ~30,000 departures.

5.2 Deutsche Bahn API

The official DB Timetables API [6] provides real-time data with endpoints `/plan/{eva_no}/{date}/{hour}` for planned departures in XML and `/fchg/{eva_no}` for changes such as delays and platform switches. This real-time delay data is used to update the static GTFS information. Each departure receives predicate `t:hasSource "db_api"` to distinguish it from GTFS data.

6 Implementation

This section details the technical implementation of the system's three main components: the backend server, RDF triple store, and frontend applications.

6.1 Backend (FastAPI Server)

The backend implements three core components:

- (1) **GTFS Loader** – downloading of static data, csv parsing, filtering, route plotting and error handling;
- (2) **DB API Client** – realtime fetching of delays, XML parsing and merging of dynamic and static data;
- (3) **Caching Layer** – in-memory caches for trip routes, station data, and route geometries, plus Oxigraph persistence via `t:TripRoutesCache`.

REST endpoints provide service statistics, station search with Unicode normalization, departures, station

lists for map display, train data, and reload triggers (Table 3).

Endpoint	Method	Function
/api/status	GET	Service health & statistics
/api/autocomplete	GET	Station search
/api/departures	GET	Station departures
/api/stations	GET	All stations
/api/gtfs-stats	GET	GTFS statistics
/api/load-gtfs	POST	Manual reload of GTFS data

Table 3 REST API Endpoints

6.2 RDF Triple Store

Oxigraph, an in-memory and persistent RDF store written in Rust, handles typical data volumes of ~30,000 departures and ~450 stations with average query times <100ms and batch inserts of 500 triples per request for stability.

6.3 Frontend and Mobile

The React 18 frontend uses TypeScript, Vite, Leaflet.js for maps, TanStack Query for state management, and nginx for production serving. Main components:

Map.tsx – for Leaflet integration with custom markers, two map layers, dark mode;

Departures.tsx – for infinite scroll, date separators, 30-second auto-refresh;

ServiceStatus.tsx – for WebSocket realtime updates and loading badges;

Autocomplete.tsx – for search and Unicode normalization.

A React Native mobile app for iOS and Android provides native map rendering, shared API client and offline caching. The final user interface is shown in Figure 2.

7 Results

The implemented system offers many features and demonstrates high performance across all components.

7.1 Feature Set

The system delivers a large set of features for real-time public transport information:

Fully Implemented:

- Interactive map
- Station search with autocomplete
- Departure boards
- WebSocket updates
- Knowledge graph
- Mobile apps
- Dark mode and rail visualisation
- Route visualisation
- Live train positions

In Development:

- Delay predictions
- Extended support to European, local, and regional trains

7.2 Performance Metrics

The system demonstrates excellent performance across startup, API response times, and database operations:

Startup:

- Cold start: ~30s
- With cache: ~5s
- GTFS download: ~10s
- RDF generation: ~15s
- Batch insert: ~5s

API Response Times:

- /api/stations: ~50ms
- /api/departures: ~100ms
- /api/autocomplete: ~30ms
- WebSocket: 2s interval

Database:

- Oxigraph volume: ~50 MB with caches
- N-Triples: ~2.5 MB of data

8 Technical Challenges

During development, several technical challenges were identified and resolved. The following subsections describe the most significant issues and their solutions.

Figure 2 Final user interface showing the interactive map, departure board, and station search functionality

8.1 Unicode Normalization

Station search functionality needed to properly handle German umlauts and special characters.

Problem: Umlauts such as München and Köln not found in searches.

Solution: SPARQL `LCASE()` and Python `unicodedata.normalize()`.

8.2 Multiple Stop IDs

Large stations often have multiple GTFS stop identifiers representing different platforms or areas.

Problem: Munich Central has 3 GTFS Stop IDs for different platforms: 631852, 236315, and 365953.

Solution: Consolidation with `FILTER(?stopId IN (...))` in SPARQL.

8.3 WebSocket vs. HTTP Polling

Real-time updates required an efficient communication strategy between frontend and backend.

Problem: HTTP polling every 3s generated 1,200 requests/hour per client.

Solution: WebSocket reduces to 1 persistent connection, achieving 99.92% fewer requests.

9 Discussion and Conclusion

This project proves RDF's transport viability via a modular semantic pipeline combining API analysis, YARRRML/RDF knowledge graph design, and app development to integrate static GTFS with real-time DB updates.

Key achievements include dual-source data integration, performance optimization with caching, WebSockets, and batch processing. The system currently supports long-distance trains across 439 stations, processing ~30,000 triples with query times <100ms.

Limitations and Future Work: German transport (~1.5M trips) requires database optimization. A planned extension is ML-based delay predictions.

Key Insights:

(1) **Viability:** Semantic Web technologies are viable for real-world applications;

(2) **Modern Rules:** YARRRML and Morph-KGC offer efficient alternatives to manual RDF generation;

(3) **WebSockets:** Improvement of performance compared to polling;

(4) **Docker Compose:** Ideal for multicontainer development.

The production-ready system offers complete documentation and a modular architecture for future extensions.

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